

Aromatic Nucleophilic Substitution Reaction. Part-I. Rates of SN_2 Reaction of 3-Nitro-4-Chloro Benzaldehyde with Sodium Phenoxides

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The kinetics of the reaction between 3-nitro-4-chlorobenzaldehyde with sodium phenoxides in ethanol have been determined. The energy and entropy of activation have been calculated. The greater reactivity of thiophenoxide ion has been explained. Linear relationship between the nucleophilic reactivities and basicities (expressed in terms of pK_a -s' of the conjugated acids) has been observed. The applicability of the Hammett equation has been studied. A linear relationship between ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger has been observed. An attempt has been made to correlate the rate constants with the oxidation potential of the nucleophiles.

Bimolecular nucleophilic substitution reactions have been extensively studied by various authors¹⁻⁵. Bunnett and co-workers^{6,7} have reviewed the extensive literature on the activating effect of the nitro group in aromatic nucleophilic substitution. They have shown that the chlorine atom in 2,4-dinitro chlorobenzene is very active. The activating power of *p*-CHO group has been studied by Miller⁸.

The present work deals with the reaction of sodium phenoxide with 3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde in ethanol. The reaction follows second order kinetics or first order with respect to each reactant.

The order of reactivity of the substituents in the phenol nucleus conforms to the following sequence :

It has been pointed out by Miller⁸ that in aromatic SN reactions the activating power of the substituents are of the following order

We have verified the prediction of Miller by treating sodium phenoxide with 3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde and 3-nitro 4-chloro acetophenone. The rate of reaction of 3-nitro 4-chloro benzaldehyde is nearly 3 times faster than that of 3-nitro 4-chloro acetophenone (Table 2).

*Greater reactivity of sodium thiophenoxide** : The rate of the reaction of 3-nitro 4-chloro benzaldehyde with sodium thiophenoxide and sodium *p*-chloro thiophenoxide have been measured in ethanol. The results have been noted in Table 3. The greater reactivity of thiophenoxide ion may be explained as follows. Negative ions having very polarisable sulfur are usually stronger nucleophiles. Besides, the desolvation due to favourable charge to size ratio is relatively easy accounting for higher reactivity of thiophenoxide ion.

TABLE 1

Values of the specific reaction rate, energy of activation, frequency factor, enthalpy of activation and entropy of activation for substituted phenoxides

Sl. No.	Substituent	$k \times 10^4$ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹ in °C					E _a K. Cal/ mole	ΔH^\ddagger K. Cal/ mole	$-\Delta S^\ddagger_{40^\circ}$ e.u.	$\Delta F^\ddagger_{40^\circ}$ K. Cal/ mole
		30	35	40	45	50				
1.	H	0.94	1.26	1.83	2.56	—	16.04	15.41	26.48	23.82
2.	<i>p</i> -Cl	—	0.93	1.41	2.21	3.63	19.34	18.71	16.44	23.86
3.	<i>o</i> -Cl	—	0.90	1.49	2.28	3.77	18.42	17.79	19.28	23.82
4.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	3.64	6.02	8.91	—	—	15.18	14.55	26.08	23.71
5.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	1.74	4.45	6.23	—	—	14.72	14.09	29.95	23.46
6.	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	2.83	4.48	6.63	—	—	14.26	13.63	29.62	22.89
7.	<i>o</i> -CHO	—	—	0.47	0.72	1.54	20.73	20.10	10.48	23.37
8.	<i>m</i> -CHO	—	—	1.32	2.13	3.63	18.88	18.25	18.04	23.90
9.	<i>p</i> -CHO	—	—	0.67	1.08	1.73	19.70	19.07	16.79	24.33

TABLE 2

Rates of reaction of sodium phenoxide with 3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde and 3-nitro 4-chloro acetophenone in ethanol at 30°

	$k \times 10^5$ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
3-nitro 4-chloro benzaldehyde	9.40
3-nitro 4-chloro acetophenone	3.15

Application to Brønsted Catalysis Law : Although no general correlation is found between nucleophilic reactivity and basicity towards protons, close relations are usually observed when the rates of reactions of a series of similar nucleophiles are compared. Thus, the Brønsted equation⁹

$$\log k = \alpha pK_a + \text{Constant}$$

(where α is the substrate constant, here it is α_N) which was originally applied to general acid base catalysis¹⁰ has been applied successfully to acylation, phosphorylation¹¹ and alkylation¹².

* We are thankful to the learned referee for kindly suggesting the interpretation for the greater reactivity of thiophenoxide ion.

The observed correlation between the basicity and the nucleophilicity for different nucleophiles (phenols) could be shown graphically by plotting the logarithm of the rate constant against pKa values¹³ of the corresponding conjugated acids in water. The results are noted in Table 4. Good Brönsted plot was obtained for this reaction, the values of α_N being 0.564. The high value of α_N implies a greater degree of bond formation in the SN_2 transition state¹⁴.

Theoretical calculation of α_N : The value of α_N can also be calculated theoretically by the method suggested by Hudson^{15,16}, by assuming reasonable transition state structures for the reaction between phenoxide and 3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde and by representing the interaction energy between the nucleophile and the electrophilic centre by Coulomb forces¹⁷. In order to set up the transition state the following assumptions were made¹⁶

- i) Consider the SN_2 transition state to be symmetrical owing to similar electronegativities of the groups 'Nu' and X and to be formed by a stretching of the C-X bond requiring the energy E_1 to give the bond $C^+ - X^-$ followed by interaction with the nucleophile (Nu).
- ii) The nucleophile (Nu) and the leaving group X share the negative charge i.e., there is no accumulation of charge in the rest of the molecule.
- iii) The N-C distance (r_1) in the transition state is the mean of the covalent and ionic radii¹⁷.

$$r_1 = \frac{1}{2} [r_{e-x} + r_{e^+x^-}] \approx r_{e-x} + 0.4A^\circ.$$

These assumptions lead to the following transition state as illustrated below :

In general case, if the charge in the nucleophilic atom (i.e., oxygen atom of the phenoxide ion) is Z and that on the electrophilic centre is δ , the activation energy ΔE^\ddagger is given by¹⁵

$$\Delta E^\ddagger = \left[Z \cdot \frac{\delta}{r_1} \cdot D \right] + E_1 \quad \dots (1)$$

Where E_1 is the energy required to stretch the C-X bond and D is the effective dielectric constant between 'Nu' and the reaction centre. Similarly for the combination of 'Nu' with a proton, the heat of reaction ΔH is given by¹⁵,

$$\Delta H = \frac{Z}{r_0} \cdot D \quad \dots (2)$$

Where r_0 is the equilibrium separation distance HN.

Combining these two equations, we get

$$\Delta E^\ddagger = (r_0/r_1) \cdot \delta \Delta H + \text{Constant}$$

or by neglecting entropy differences,

$$\log k = (r_0/r_1) \cdot pK_a + \text{constant.}$$

Thus, from r_0 , r_1 and the assumed transition-state structure, computed value of $(r_0/r_1) \cdot \delta$ can be compared with the experimental value of the Brönsted α (see Table 4).

Hammett equation : The observed rate constant for various substituted phenoxide ions for 40° are described in Table 1. The rate determined for meta- and para-substituted compounds fit Hammett equation¹⁸ very closely giving correlation coefficient (r) = 0.98 and standard deviation (s) = 0.011, and $\rho = -2.37$ and indicating that electron donating group enhances the reaction rate. The high negative value of ρ conform to pronounced substituent effect on rate.

Edwards equation : For atoms other than hydrogen atom the standard Edwards equation¹⁹

$$\log k/k_0 = \alpha E_n + \beta H$$

may be deduced to the following form

$$\log k/k_0 = \alpha E_n$$

where E_n is the standard electrode potential value of the nucleophile. In the absence of large number of E_n values, we have only included a very small number of nucleophiles in the present investigation. The E_n values together with the rate data of the nucleophiles are given in Table 7. The rate data of these nucleophiles at 45° have been plotted against the electrode potential values. An excellent plot is obtained. The high value of α (0.99) indicates that the bond formation is stronger in the transition state than in the reactant state²⁰.

TABLE 3

Rates of reaction of thiophenoxide and p-Cl thiophenoxide with 3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde

Name of the compound	Temp. °C	$k \times 10^3$ lit. mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹
Thiophenoxide	15	11.82
Do-	20	27.03
Do-	25	38.38
p-Cl thiophenoxide	15	2.03
Do-	20	8.88
Do-	25	14.73

Relationship between enthalpy of activation and entropy of activation : A mere glance to Table 1 indicates that ΔF^\ddagger values are nearly invariant, the corresponding variation in ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger are certainly beyond the experimental error. The nature of variation in

ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger is suggestive of the fact that the overall rates are largely governed by co-operative efforts²¹. Analogous argument has been advanced very recently by Talukdar *et al.*²² in the hydrolysis study of azorhodanines.

TABLE 4

Calculated and observed values of Brönsted parameter α_N

Nature of the reaction	$r_1(A^\circ)$	$r_0(A^\circ)$	α_N (Cald.)	α_N (Found)
SN ₂	1.83	1.76	0.49	0.56

A linear relationship between the entropy of activation and enthalpy of activation has been found in the present reaction for all the compounds except 4. In the equation

$$\Delta H^\ddagger(E) = \Delta H^\ddagger_0(E_0) + \beta \Delta S^\ddagger$$

ΔH^\ddagger has the value 31.27 K.Cal mole⁻¹ and β , the value 350°K with $r = 0.992$ and $s = 0.113$. The continuous relationship shown by the majority of compounds signifies a mechanism constant in its main details^{23,24}.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-nitro-4-chloro benzaldehyde was prepared according to the method of Hodgson²⁵.

The sodium phenoxides were prepared from sodium ethoxide and substituted phenols¹⁴. The sodium salt was filtered, washed with ethanol and then dried in vacuum to constant weight in a tared flask at 100°–110°.

TABLE 5

Values of E_n and k_{45} for different nucleophiles

Nucleophiles	$k_{45} \times 10^4$ lit.mole ⁻¹ sec ⁻¹	E_n
C ₆ H ₅ O [⊖]	2.56	1.46
CH ₃ COO [⊖]	1.44	0.95
Cl-CH ₂ COO [⊖]	1.23	0.79
(<i>p</i>) CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ O [⊖]	12.02	0.84

Kinetic measurement : 25 ml of a solution of 0.02 (*M*) chloro compound and 0.04 (*M*) with respect to the phenoxide solution in ethanol were preheated in a thermostat in order to attain the temperature of the bath. 25 ml of the phenoxide solution was then added to the chloro compound and the reaction started. The SN₂ reactions were followed by pipetting 5 ml aliquots of reaction mixture into 10 ml of 10% aqueous nitric acid and then titrating the chloride ion by Volhard's method. The rate data were computed graphically by a plot of $\log[(a-x)/(b-x)]$ against time. The measured rate constants were all accurate to within 2–3% by agreement between duplicate experiments. The activation parameters were calculated by using appropriate equations²⁶. The values of E_n and ΔH^\ddagger were computed with an accuracy of ± 0.5 K.Cal/mole and ΔS^\ddagger of 0.8 entropy unit. The values of rate constant together with the activation parameters are recorded in Table 1.

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